

Carbon Sequestration by Mangrove Vegetation: A Case Study from Odisha Bhitarkanika Wild Life Sanctuary (BWLS)

Kakoli Banerjee^{1*}, Gobinda Bal^{1✉}, Nabonita Pal^{2†}, Gahul Amin^{3‡} and Abhijit Mitra^{4◇}

¹Department of Biodiversity & Conservation of Natural Resources, Central University of Orissa, Landiguda, Koraput, Odisha, 764021, India.

²Department of Oceanography, Techno India University, Salt Lake Campus, Kolkata, 700091, India.

³School of Sciences, Netaji Subhas Open University, Kalyani Campus, Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal, India.

⁴Department of Marine Science, University of Calcutta, 35 B.C. Road, Kolkata, 700019, India.

Abstract

Bhitarkanika Wild Life Sanctuary (BWLS) is a unique mangrove dominated forest patch in Odisha, a maritime state in the north east part of India. Carbon sequestration in 29 true mangrove floral species was estimated based on the stored carbon in the stem region of the documented species in 2012 and 2016. We willingly avoided the estimation of stored carbon in the branches, twigs and leaves as these above ground structures are relatively semi-permanent in nature (unlike the stout stem of the tree) and contribute to litter and detritus that are ultimately buried under the soil or drain out to the adjacent estuary. The carbon sequestration rate is approximately $10.92 \text{ t ha}^{-1}\text{y}^{-1}$ by the stem region of the mangrove trees, which represents $40.08 \text{ t ha}^{-1}\text{y}^{-1}$ carbon dioxide equivalent.

Keywords: Bhitarkanika Wild Life Sanctuary (BWLS), Carbon dioxide equivalent, Carbon sequestration, Mangroves.

* E-mail: banerjee.kakoli@yahoo.com

✉ E-mail: balgobinda@gmail.com

† E-mail: nabonita.pal2014@gmail.com

‡ E-mail: amintony@gmail.com

◇ E-mail: abhijit_mitra@hotmail.com

1. Introduction

One of the major environmental issues in the present century is climate change, which has several adverse impacts like rise of atmospheric temperature, retreat of glaciers, weather extremes, sea level rise, acidification of sea water, and spread of parasitic diseases. The average carbon dioxide level of the atmosphere is 407.25 ppm (as on July, 2017), which is about 45.5% higher than pre-industrial level of 280 ppm (<https://www.co2.earth/annual-co2>) The rise of carbon dioxide can be retarded to a great extent through carbon sequestration by autotrophs. Mangroves are specialized autotrophs found at the land-sea interface and can tolerate high degree of salinity (~35 psu). They are known as halophytes and possess few distinctive features like presence of pneumatophores, silt root, prop root, viviparous germination etc.

The total area covered by mangrove vegetation in the planet earth is ~ 138,000 km² (Giri *et al.*, 2010). India has considerable chunk of mangrove forests most of which are concentrated in the east coast of the country (2,75,800 ha). The present study is an approach to evaluate carbon sequestration in the stem region of major mangrove species present in the BWLS, Odisha. The approach is undoubtedly an underestimation in the domain of mangrove carbon sequestration, as carbon is also stored in the branches, twigs and leaves of the trees. However, because of difficulty in sampling due to presence of crocodiles in the intertidal mudflats, we concentrated only on the sequestered carbon in the stem region, which is easy to measure without getting in the mudflats for several hours of time. Another reason of estimating carbon in the stem region is the permanent characteristics of this vegetative part, unlike branches and leaves, which are transformed into litter and detritus very frequently and are transferred to underlying soil compartment (burial) or adjacent waterbodies (as particulate organic carbon, dissolved organic carbon and dissolved inorganic carbon).

2. Materials and methods

BWLS is situated on the east coast of India in the maritime state of Odisha in the district Kendrapara.

The sanctuary lies between 20°4'N to 20°8'N latitude and 86°45'E to 87°50'E longitude covering a geographical area of approximately 672 sq.km., out of which ~150 sq.km is covered by mangroves (Fig. 1 and 2).

Figure 1. Map showing the study site at Bhitarkanika Mangrove Ecosystem.

The climate of the region is tropical humid with three main seasons namely premonsoon, monsoon and postmonsoon. The average annual rainfall is around 1670 mm of which ~75% occurs during the months of August and September.

2.1. Sampling

Simple random sampling method was used to collect the samples. Sample plots were laid along line transects based on tidal variation in the study area. 15

random sampling plots of 10 m × 10 m were selected on the intertidal mudflats. To evaluate the stored carbon in the stem biomass, the taxonomic diversity, population density and stem biomass of all the true mangrove floral species were recorded. The sampling was carried out during low tide period and only the live trees with a diameter at breast height (DBH) ≥ 5 cm were recorded.

2.2. Estimation of stem biomass

The DBH was measured at breast height, which is 1.3 m from the ground level. It was measured by using tree calliper and measuring tape.

Trees with multiple stems connected near the ground were counted as single individuals and bole circumference was measured separately. Stem height was recorded by using laser based height measuring instrument (model BOSCH). The methodology and procedures to estimate the stem biomass of the selected true mangrove tree species were carried out step by step as per the VACCIN project manual of CSIR (Mitra and Sunderasan, 2016) considering and measuring parameters like DBH, DBR (Diameter of basal region), height of the stem, density of the stem wood and form factor. The population density of

each species was also documented to express the value of stem biomass in $t\ ha^{-1}$.

2.3. Estimation of stem carbon

Direct estimation of percent carbon in the stem was done by *Vario MACRO elemental* CHN analyzer, after grinding and random mixing the oven dried stems from 15 different sampling plots. The estimation was done separately for each species and mean values were expressed as $t\ ha^{-1}$.

2.4. Estimation of carbon sequestration

Carbon sequestration is defined as the rate of change of stored carbon with time. In the present study, estimation of stored carbon in the stem of the selected mangrove trees was done during August 2012 and August 2016 in the same locations. Hence the rate of change of stored carbon in the stem biomass of the selected species (carbon sequestration) was calculated by dividing the difference in stored carbon between years with the time factor (4 years in this case).

Figure 2. Mangrove patch at BWLS with litter scattered on the intertidal mudflats.

3. Results

3.1. Taxonomic diversity

A total of 29 true mangrove floral species were documented from the study area and the population density (in No./100 m²) ranged from 0.15 (*Thespesia populnea*) to 30.12 (*Heritiera fomes*) in 2012 and 0.08 (*Lumnitzera racemosa*) to 28.85 (*Heritiera fomes*) in 2016 as shown in Fig 3.

Figure 3. Taxonomic diversity of mangrove trees in Bhitarkanika; the blue bar represents the population density (in No./100m²) in 2016 and the green bar represents the population density (in No./100m²) in 2012.

3.2. Stem biomass

The stem biomass values computed for all the 29 species ranged from 0.02 t ha⁻¹ (in case of *Tamarix troupii*) to 7.74 t ha⁻¹ (in case of *Sonneratia apetala*) in 2012 and 0.7 t ha⁻¹ (in case of *Thespesia populnea*) to 25.16 t ha⁻¹ (in case of *Avicennia officinalis*) in 2016. The order is represented in Fig 4.

Figure 4. Stem biomass of mangrove trees in Bhitarkanika; the black bar represents the stem biomass (t ha⁻¹) in 2016 and the red bar represents the stem biomass (t ha⁻¹) in 2012.

3.3. Stem carbon

The stored carbon in the stem of the selected species varied from 3.64 t ha⁻¹ (in *Sonneratia apetala*) to 0.01 (in *Tamarix troupii* and *Thespesia populnea*) in 2012 and in 2016 it ranged from 0.03 t ha⁻¹ in *Thespesia populnea* to 11.32 t ha⁻¹ in *Avicennia officinalis* as shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Stem carbon of mangrove trees in Bhitarkanika; the purple bar represents the stem biomass (t ha⁻¹) in 2016 and the yellow bar represents the stem biomass (t ha⁻¹) in 2012.

3.4. Carbon sequestration

Carbon sequestration was estimated for each of the 29 true mangrove species based on the stored carbon values of 2012 and 2016 (time span of four years). The graphical representation is shown in Fig 6.

Figure 6. Carbon sequestration by mangrove trees in Bhitarkanika.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

Mangroves are forests with rich productivity. These forests play a major role in coastal and global carbon cycling and therefore an in-depth analysis of stored carbon in the mangrove biomass is essential. The greatest uncertainty in understanding this process is the issue of carbon allocation in the root region, which is difficult to measure in this rigorous environment with waterlogged soils. Also the process is destructive in nature as it requires uprooting the trees. Hence, in this paper we attempted to estimate the stored carbon in the stem region of true mangrove floral species of BWLS during 2012 and 2016 (a gap of four years). From these two data sets, the carbon sequestered value was estimated to be $10.92 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ y}^{-1}$. The species-wise order of carbon sequestration is represented in Fig. 6. This value is slightly less than the study conducted by several researchers in this domain (Alongi *et al.*, 2000; 2004; 2008; Alongi, 2011; Clough, 1998). All these values have been estimated considering the AGB (t C ha^{-1}) and age (in years) of the selected mangrove floral species and hence cannot be compared in scale with the values obtained by our team members as we have estimated the carbon sequestered only in the stem region. We focused on the carbon locked in the stem and did not consider the carbon reservoir in the branches, twigs and leaves of mangrove mainly because of the fact that stem is relatively permanent in nature compared to other above ground structures like branches, twigs and leaves, which contribute to litter/detritus and get transformed into particulate organic carbon (POC), dissolved organic carbon (DOC) dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) and detritus on the intertidal mudflats (Fig. 7).

The data presented in this study confirm the fact that BWLS mangroves are among the most carbon rich ecosystems in the tropics and therefore needs to be conserved by reducing threats that arise from clearing of mangroves patches, conversion to industrial/aquaculture units, changing drainage patterns etc. Such activities result in considerable emission of carbon dioxide to the atmosphere, which may otherwise exceed the carbon dioxide equivalent value of $40.08 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ y}^{-1}$ as observed for the present geographical locale.

Figure 7. Branches twigs and leaves of mangroves contribute to litter, POC, DOC and DIC. Drawing by Dr. Prosenjit Pramanick, Scientist, TIU, WB.

References

- [1] Alongi D. M. **Carbon payments for mangrove conservation:** ecosystem constraints and uncertainties of sequestration potential. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 14, 462–470 (2011).
- [2] Alongi D. M, Trott L. A, Rachmansyah, Tirendi F., McKinnon A. D. & Undu M. C. **Growth and development of mangrove forests overlying smothered coral reefs, Sulawesi and Sumatra, Indonesia.** *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 370, 97–109 (2008).
- [3] Alongi D.M. & Dixon P. **Mangrove primary production and above - and below - ground biomass in Sawi Bay, southern Thailand.** *Phuket Mar. Biol. Cent. Sp. Publ.* 22, 31–38 (2000).
- [4] Alongi D. M., Sasekumar A., Chong V. C., Pfitzner J., Trott L.A., Tirendi F., Dixon P. &

Brunskill G. J. **Sediment accumulation and organic material flux in a managed mangrove ecosystem: estimates of land–ocean–atmosphere exchange in peninsular Malaysia.** *Mar. Geol.* 208, 383–402 (2004).

[5] Clough B. F. **Mangrove forest productivity and biomass accumulation in Hinchinbrook Channel, Australia.** *Mangroves Salt Marshes* 2,191–198 (1998).

[6] Giri C., Ochieng E., Tiszen L. L., Zhu Z., Singh A., Loveland T., Masek J. & Duke N. **Status and**

distribution of mangrove forests of the world using earth observation satellite data. *Glob. Ecol. Biogeogr.* 20,154–159 (2010).

[7] Mitra A. & Sundaresan J. **How to study stored carbon in mangroves published by CSIR-National Institute of Science Communication and Information Resources (NISCAIR).** ISBN: 978-81-7236-349-9 (2016).

[8] CO₂.Earth is an independent, citizen-led initiative. **Annual CO₂ Data.** <<https://www.co2.earth/annual-co2>>. 2017.